
**USE OF E-RESOURCES IN TEACHING AND LEARNING
AMONG FACULTY MEMBERS: A SURVEY**

Dr. Kumara B

Assistant Librarian,

University Library, Tumkur University, Tumakuru.

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.13120460

Abstract:

The present paper explores use of e-Resources in teaching and learning among Faculty members. A total of 301 samples were selected from the affiliated degree colleges in Tumkur University of Karnataka state. A well designed questionnaire was used for the data collection and data has been analyzed using SPSS (27.0). The study found that most of the male (60.5%) and female (39.5%) respondents are used e-Resources. The table also clearly indicates that the majority of the respondents are from the rural areas (77.7%). The study found that most of the respondents used e-resources at their home(52.1%) and 64.3% of the respondents spent less than 2 hours. The most of the respondents are always preferred to online databases (Exp: N-List-57.8%). The present study found that almost all the respondents used e-resources for various purposes for the research, to update knowledge, for seminar/assignments, to prepare notes and to prepare for examinations.

Keywords: e-Resources, Professor, e-books, Education.

Introduction:

The advent of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has enhanced the availability and usage of e-resources among the academic community in recent years globally. There has been a rapid demand of the user community to get more and more information online. The development of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) changed the relevant philosophy for collection development in the context of the fourth law of library science “save the time of the reader/ staff” in which S. R. Ranganathan

recognized an objective relating to the internal efficiency of the libraries. When a resource is available on the desktop it can save a trip to the library, and therefore, be perceived as saving time (Van Epps, 2005).

Electronic resources are the electronic representation of information. They are available in various forms like e-books, digital libraries, online journal magazines, e-learning tutors and online tests. Because of their effective presentation with multimedia tools, these e-resources have become important and effective sources of

information. Electronic resources form collection of information in libraries as full text databases, e-journals, image collections, multimedia in the form of CD, tape, internet, web technology, e-discussions, e-news, data archives, e-mail, even online chatting(Sharma, 2019).

Review of Literature:

Partap and Ranga (2021) conducted a study on “awareness and use of e-resources at Chandigarh College of Architecture, Chandigarh, India: A study”. Total 150 questionnaires were distributed and 127 questionnaires were received back by respondents. More than 90% respondents were aware about the use of e-resources and using in their academic and research work. Majority of the respondents (95%) were satisfied with the use of e-resources.

Kumara et.al (2019) examined the study found that most of the respondents read books at home (69.1%). The study found that most of the respondents have a positive opinion on the use of e-sources than print sources. Most of the respondents opined that e-sources are cheaper than print sources, through electronic sources the information is available 24/7, e-sources provide voluminous information and they are easy to carry. Kumara & Manjunatha (2019) in their study found that almost all the respondents read library sources for the examination
Dr. Kumara B

(100%) purpose and most of them preferred to read books/periodicals (99.5%).

Manjunatha and Sampath Kumar(2019) investigates the study found tht, most of the respondents have 1-2 years of experience in using e-journals and majority of respondents use ejournals occasionally. Most of the respondents used e-journals in the college libraries. Therefore the college library should organize orientation programs to create awareness about e-journal among the students and faculty members.

Borgohain and Barman (2016) examined the knowledge and Use of E-Resources by Faculty and Research Students at the Dibrugarh University and found that the majority of the faculties are aware of the e-resources available in the university. It is further found that the faculty uses e-resources in their teaching process. E-journals and online databases are the most preferred type of e-resource among faculty members.

Joseph and Sornam (2016) conducted the study in use of e-resources by the faculty members of engineering colleges in Kerala on 15 different engineering colleges in Kerala. The study shows that majorities of the faculty are frequent users of e-resources and all faculty members make use of e-resources for teaching purposes while some faculty members also make use of

e-resources for research purpose, general information and career advancement.

Objectives of the Study:

The main objectives of the present study are;

- To know the of use of e-resources among the faculty members.
- To know the frequency of use of e-resources by the faculty members.
- To know the types of e-resources used by the faculty members.
- To know the purpose of use of e-resources among the faculty members.

Methodology:

The total strength of the faculty members from the affiliated degree colleges at Tumkur university was 1382 for the academic year 2022-23. There are several formula for calculating the required sample size. This study has followed the formula given by Krejcie and Morgan (1970).

$$s = \frac{x^2 NP(1 - P)}{d^2(N - 1) + x^2 P(1 - P)}$$

s = required sample size.

x^2 = the table value of Chi-square for 1 degree of freedom at the desired confidence level (3.84).

N = the population size (1382).

P = the population proportion (assumed to be 0.50 since this would provide the maximum sample size).

Dr. Kumara B

d = the degree of accuracy expressed as 'p' (i.e. Margin of error=0.05)

$$s = \frac{3.84 \times 1382 \times 0.05 (1 - 0.05)}{(0.025)^2(1381 - 1) + (3.82) (0.05) (1 - 0.05)}$$

s=301

The sample size has been calculated using the above mentioned formula. The required sample size was 301 (Degree of accuracy/margin of error=0.05 and confidence=95.0%). This primary data gathered through a structured questionnaire. A well designed questionnaire was used for the data collection and data has been analyzed using SPSS (27.0).

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

The data presented in the table-1 shows the demographic information of the respondents. The study population consisted of most the respondents are male (60.5%) and female (39.5%) respondents. The study clearly indicates that the majority of the respondents are from the rural areas (77.7%) and only 22.3% of respondents are from urban areas. Further, the table also reveals that, 39.9% of the respondents are from Arts, followed by Commerce (33.9%) and Science (26.2%) faculty. Further, the table shows that 47.1% of the respondents are in the age group of 31-40 years, 28.9% of them are in the age group of below 30 years.

**Table-1: Demographic information
of the respondents**

Demographic information		Frequency (N=301)	Percentage
Gender	Male	182	60.5
	Female	119	39.5
Social background	Rural	234	77.7
	Urban	67	22.3
Faculty	Arts	120	39.9
	Science	79	26.2
	Commerce	102	33.9
Age groups	20-30	87	28.9
	31-40	142	47.1
	41-50	51	16.9
	>51	21	7.0

**Table-2: Educational background of
the respondents**

Educations	Frequency	Percentage
Post Graduation	222	73.8
M.Phil	57	18.9
Ph.D	22	7.3
Total	301	100

The educational background of respondents are presented in the table-2. It is found that majority of the respondents obtained Post Graduation (73.8%), followed by 18.9% of them have pursued M.Phil degree and only 7.3% of them have PhD degree.

The designation of respondents is presented in table-3. The study found that, most of the respondents are Guest Faculty (51.8%), followed by Assistant Professor (43.5%) and only 4.7% are Associate Professors.

Dr. Kumara B

Table-3: Designation of respondents

Designation	Frequency	Percentage
Associate	14	4.7
Professor		
Assistant Professor	131	43.5
Guest Faculty	156	51.8
Total	301	100.0

**Table-4: Frequency of use of e-
resources(N=286)**

Frequency	Frequency	Percentage
Every day	104	36.4
2-3 days in a week	52	18.2
Once in a week	62	21.7
Once in a month	5	1.7
Occasionally	63	22.0
Total	286	100.0

Frequency of use of e-resource by respondents is presented in the table-4. The study found that 36.4% of the respondents used e-sources every day, followed by occasionally (22.0%), once in a week (21.7%), 2-3 days in a week (18.2%) and few of them used e-sources also once in a month (1.7%).

The preferred places of use of e-resources by respondents is presented in the table-5. The study found that most of the respondents used e-resources at their *home*(52.1%), followed by *departments* (28.7 %), *cybercafe* (10.1%)

and few of them used e-resources at library (9.1%).

Table-5: Preferred places of use of e-resources by the male and female (N=286)

Preferred places	Frequency	Percentage
Home	149	52.1
Departments	82	28.7
Library	26	9.1
Cybercafe	29	10.1
Total	286	100

Table-6: Time spent in the use of e-resources

Time duration	Frequency (N=286)	Percentage
<2 hours	184	64.3
3-4 hours	70	24.5
>5hours	32	11.2
Total	286	100.0

Time spent in the use of e-resources is presented in the table-6. The notable findings of the study show that, 64.3% of the respondents spent less than 2 hours per day, followed by 3-4 hours (24.5%) and few of them spent more than 5 hours (11.2%).

Table-7: Types of e-resources preferred to use

Types of e-sources	Always	Often	Some times	Rarely	Never
E-books	92 (32.2%)	78 (27.3%)	62 (21.7%)	20 (7.0%)	34 (11.9%)
E-journals	91 (31.8%)	77 (26.9%)	60 (21.0%)	33 (11.5%)	25 (8.7%)
Online Databases (Exp: N-List, E-shodhsindhu)	126 (44.1%)	58 (20.3%)	50 (17.5%)	30 (10.5%)	22 (7.7%)
E-theses/dissertations	87 (30.4%)	45 (15.7%)	47 (16.4%)	74 (25.9%)	33 (11.5%)
E-newspaper/magazines	78 (27.3%)	67 (23.4%)	44 (15.4%)	53 (18.5%)	44 (15.4%)

Types of e-resources preferred to used by respondents are presented in the table-7. The present study found that all most all the respondents preferred to use of e-resources. The most of the respondents are always preferred to Online Databases (Exp: N-List, E-shodhsindhu) (57.8%), followed by E-

books (32.2),e-journals (31.8%) E-theses/dissertations (30.1%), and few of them always preferred to used E-newspaper/magazines (27.3 %).

The purpose of use of e-resources by respondents is presented in the table 8. The present study found that almost all the respondents used e-resources for

various purposes. The table clearly shows that, 52.8% of the respondents used e-resources for research purpose and to update knowledge (51.7%). Further, the study result shows that,

48.3% of the respondents used e-resources to prepare for seminar/assignments, personal use(38.1%), to prepare notes(37.4%) to prepare for examination(33.9%) purpose.

Table-8: Purpose of use of e-resources

Purpose of use of e-resources	To a great extent	To full extent	To little extent	To some extent	Not at all
To prepare for examination	97 (33.9%)	91 (31.8%)	65 (22.7%)	22 (7.7%)	11 (3.8%)
To update knowledge	148 (51.7%)	61 (21.3%)	48 (16.8%)	9 (3.1%)	20 (7.0%)
For research purpose	151 (52.8%)	40 (14.0%)	58 (20.3%)	24 (8.4%)	13 (4.5%)
To prepare for seminar/assignments	138 (48.3%)	76 (26.6%)	55 (19.2%)	14 (4.9%)	3 (1.0%)
To prepare notes	107 (37.4%)	82 (28.7%)	66 (23.1%)	11 (3.8%)	20 (7.0%)
Personal Use	109 (38.1%)	94 (32.9%)	60 (21.0%)	3 (1.0%)	20 (7.0%)

Discussion and Conclusion:

The present study enlightens the use of e-resources in teaching and learning among faculty members. Firstly, The study found that most of the male and female respondents are used e-resources every day. The study found that majority of the respondents obtained Post Graduation (73.8%). In this context, the study observed that very few of them obtained PhD degree. The study recommends that, the concerned institutions/colleges, support their faculty members to obtain research degrees.

Secondly, the study found that most respondents are Guest Faculty

(51.8%) compared to permanent faculties. In this context, the study recommended that, concerned colleges and governments need to recruit teaching staff and enrich the quality of education.

Furthermore, the study found that all most all the male and female respondents have positive attitude toward use of e-resources for their academic purposes. In this context, it is suggested that concerned college authorities and library staff need to procure more e-resources to the faculty members to enhance their academic activities.

References:

1. Borgohain, Trinayan., & Barman, Nandita (2016). Knowledge and use of e-resources by faculty and research students at the Dibrugarh University, Assam. *Informatics Studies*, 3(3), pp.50-56.
2. Kumara, B., & Manjunatha, G. (2019). Use of Library sources among Dalit students: A Survey. *New Horizons of Dalit Culture and Literature*, 61.
3. Kumara, B., Sampath Kumar, B. T., & Kumbar, M. (2019). Print v/s electronic sources of information: Preferred sources for reading among faculty members and students. *Knowledge Organisation in Academic Libraries (I-KOAL 2019): Building Smart Libraries: Challenges and Discovery Tools*, 44-47.
4. Manjunatha, G., & Sampath Kumar, B. T., (2019). E-journals usage among Faculty members and Students: A Survey. *Library Philosophy and Practice*.
5. Partap, B., & Ranga, M. (2021). Awareness and use of e-resources at Chandigarh college of Architecture, Chandigarh, India: A study. *Library Philosophy and Practice*.
<https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/5564>.
6. Sharma, N. (2019). Use of e-resources by the faculty members and students: a study of Swami Shradhanand College, University of Delhi, Delhi. *Journal of Indian Library Association Now Available at <https://journal.ilaindia.net/>*, 54(3).
7. Van Epps, A. S. (2005). The evolution of electronic reference sources. *Library Hi Tech*, 23(2), 287-298.